

The Influence of Social Networking Sites on Student Educational Performance (A study on Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur)

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Paras Soomro, MS Scholor ⁽²⁾Bilawal Ali Soomro, MS Schlor

⁽³⁾Dr. Syed Muneer Ahmed Shah, Assistant Professor-Department of Business Administration Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur

Abstract: *This article investigate the influence of social networking sites (sns) on student educational performance. Structured questionnaire based on likert scale was used in business department of shah Abdul Latif University to gathered data from the sample of 165 undergraduates. Gathered data was examined through Quantitative method regression. Results demonstrate that social networking sites (SNSs) is positively and significantly influence the students' educational performance and degree of significance is .008, but the influence of social networking sites(SNSs) on students' educational performance is too much weak that is (.207). There may be other variables which influence students' academic performance.*

Key Words- social networking sites, student academic performance.

INTRODUCTION:

The social networking sites have becoming one of the most popular communication platforms in recent time periods. Social networks allow all age group of Internet consumer to becoming a part of most effective and reliable communication means. According to pew research center internet, science and Tech, 74% of adults use online social networking sites in January 2014. Educational institutions and teaching staff are using SNS for instance Face book to link with current students and former students to convey instructional stuff. According to The most favorite social networking sites are Face book, Twitter, LinkedIn, Whatsapp and others. 87.5% students including both genders have facebook accounts and consume equal time on internet, male have a lot of facebook companion but female students consume much of their time on facebook (Ahsan & Chand, 2012). These social networking sites are means to connect people globally. Now individuals, groups are closer and connected with each other, they exchange their ideas, feelings, knowledge, personal information, pictures and videos on SNSs. SNSs connect students and teachers for educational interests. Students consume much time on social networking sites which increase their social awareness, knowledge and they keep in touch with their friends. There are positive and negative aspects of social networking sites use on students' educational performance. Negative aspect is that spending much time on social networking sites for amusement purpose may influence the students' educational performance and positive aspect is that when students consume much time on social networks for enhancing their knowledge and also use SNSs for searching career opportunities and educational interests such as local or international scholarships, checking updates for admissions and other universities relate information from universities pages on SNSs.

We conducted research on undergraduate students of shah Latif University to investigate the positive or negative influences of social networking sites on students' educational performance

LITERATURE REVIEW:

P.M., J.A., & Y. (2012) they concluded from the results that usage of social networking site facebook does not negatively effect the students performance in nigeria universities.

Qing, Wei, & Yu (2011) they concluded from resaerch results that social media negatively influenced the college students because they spend more time on social media.

kalra & manani(2013) They drawn conclusion from results that social networking sites does not influence the student academic performance. There is no significant variation in educational performance of social networking sites consumer and non consumer.

Paul & Aryn(2010) they concluded from results that facebook consumers have poor GPA and consume fewer hours on study as compare to those who donot use facebook.

Ahsan & Chand(2012)study revealed that 87.5% students including both male and female have facebook account but male have a lot of facebook companion and female students consume much of their time on facebook. Use of facebook negatively influence the university students educational performance but male are affected more.

Johnson & George (2014) whatsapp use negativitly influence the student academic performance in tertiary institutions ghana because students spend more time in whatsapp which leads to lackof attention during class, poor grammar and spellings and students face difficulty in balancing the study time and online actions.

Khan (2013) concluded that person use social networking sites because of social pressure. Graduate students and those who have 3 to 3.5 GPA and also those whose age interval is 15-25 consume time on social networking sites for amusement.60% male pupils use it for knowledge.

Aghazamani(2010) found out the intention for using and spending time on facebook. Data gathered from sample 595 students who are habitual of using networking sites. Male spend much time as compare to female students on facebook. Results proved that

graduate pupils login on facebook fewer time per day than undergraduate pupil .For male undergraduate students friendship is the much loved activity.

Waqas, Madiha, Khan, & FaseeUllah (2012)they concluded from the research that education and future of adolescents are negatively affected by consuming time on social networking sites.

R., E., & G. (2010) they concluded from research results that using social networking sites especially twitter for educational purpose improve grades and student engagement.

bernd, oliver, & martin (2015) face book use during class negatively related to educational performance, that pupils placed in closely or tightly connected sub networks get better grades. Male pupils take advantage from the common use of face book when they are highly connected as compare to female students.

Dr., Parmodh, & Prem (2014)they conducted research on the post graduate students of jammu kashmir district they found insignificant relationship between score of attitude towards the SNSs use and educational performance score.

M.Kanagarathinam(2014)the finding suggested that students who consume time on social networking sites do not find problem to meet equcational requirement.

Jomon, Hope, & Justin (2012) they found that significantly negative relationship online social networking and their equcational performance ,much time spend by student on online social network less their academic performance.

Reynol (2011) facebook was negative association with engagement scale score and positive with the time consume on curricular pursuits.

Objective of Study: To examine the influence of social networking sites (SNSs) on students' educational performance. This study will demonstrate the association between social networking sites (SNSs) and students' educational performance.

STUDY MODEL:

DIAGNOSTIC TEST OF STUDY:

$$SAP = \alpha + SN\beta_1 + \mu$$

μ = standard error.

SNSs = Social networking sites

SAP = Students' educational performance

β_1 = Coefficient.

After re-examining the literature these hypotheses were made.

HYPOTHESES OF STUDY:

H0 = there is a significant and positive influence of social networking sites (SNSs) on students' educational performance.

H1: there is an insignificant and negative influence of social networking sites (SNSs) on students' educational performance.

STUDY METHODOLOGY: Two types of data sets were used in this research paper primary data and Secondary data. Primary data was collected through structured questionnaire based on likert scale included 4 demographics questions and 17 questions associate with variables. Random sampling method was used to select sample of 165 undergraduate students of business department of shah Abdul Latif University. For understanding and analyzing the Data, statistical software SPSS18's technique quantitative linear regression was used. Secondary data was gathered from academic journals, periodicals and websites for citation of references included in this research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Table 1:

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.751	17

After the test of reliability of instrument, Factor analysis technique was used to generate small factors from data which was used in linear regression

Table 2:

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.207 ^a	.043	.037		.98135378

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social networking

Table 3:

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7.022	1	7.022	7.291	.008 ^a
	Residual	156.978	163	.963		
	Total	164.000	164			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social networking

b. Dependent Variable: Students' educational Performance

Results demonstrate from model summary Adjusted R Square= .037 approximately 4% which shows weak fitness of model, error term is too large to work it out in future but ANOVA table shows the degree of significance for the fitness of model that is .008 level of significance.

Table 4:

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-1.255E-16	.076		.000	1.000
	Social Networking	.207	.077	.207	2.700	.008

a. Dependent Variable: Students' educational Performance

Score of Beta social networking, the standardized coefficient measure is .207 that is positively and significantly influences the students' educational performance. So accept the null hypothesis that is H0: there is a significant and positive influence of social networking sites on students' educational performance and reject the alternative hypothesis that is H1: there is an insignificant and negative influence of social networking sites on students' educational performance.

While evaluating the students' educational performance gap term is too large. Results demonstrate that social networking sites contribution to students' educational performance is lesser or unimportant.

RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS:

Students' educational performance should be evaluate from other variables except variable social networking sites, because it is not strongly influencing the students' educational performance, there may be many other factors which influence the students' educational performance.

LIMITATIONS:

1. Only the general university of khairpur was the area of research,
2. Only the business department of Shah Abdul University khairpur sindh Pakistan was selected for conducting the survey.
3. Resources and time utilized as per the requirement of course agenda.

REFERENCES:

- A. u., & Chand, S. (2012). Pattern of Facebook usage and its Impact on Academic Performance of University Students: A Gender Based Comparison. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 34(2), 19-28.
- Aghazamani, A. (2010). How Do University Students Spend Their Time On Facebook? An Exploratory Study. *Journal of American Science*, 6(12) , 730-735.
- b. s., o. h., & m. s. (2015). Social media and academic performance: does the intensity of Facebook activity relate to good grades? 54-72.
- D. J., P. K., & P. L. (2014). EFFECT OF USE OF SOCIAL NETWORKING SITES ON THE ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF POST-GRADUATE STUDENTS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BEHAVIORAL SOCIAL AND MOVEMENT SCIENCES*, 03(01), 74-81.
- J. A., H. M., & J. D. (2012). Effect of online social networking on student academic performance. *Computers in Human Behavior Elsevier Ltd*, 2117–2127.
- Johnson, Y., & G. D. (2014). The Impact of Whatsapp Messenger Usage on Students Performance in Tertiary Institutions in Ghana. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5 (6), 157-164.
- kalra, R. k., & manani, P. (2013). EFFECT OF SOCIAL NETWORKING SITES ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG INTROVERTS AND EXTROVERTS. *ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES & HUMANITIES*, 2(3).
- Khan, S. (2013). Impact of Social Networking Websites on Students. *Abasyn Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(2), 56-77.
- M.Kanagarathinam. (2014). Impact of Social Networking Sites on Academic Performance of Adolescents in Coimbatore city. *INDIAN JOURNAL OF APPLIED RESEARCH*, 4(12), 69-71.
- P. A., & A. C. (2009). Running head: FACEBOOK AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE. *Facebook and Academic Performanc*, 1-39.
- P. O., J. E., & Y. M. (2012). A survey on Facebook and Academic Performance in Nigeria Universities. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications*, 2(4), 788-797.
- Q. y., W. C., & Y. L. (2011). The Effects of Social Media on College Students . *The Alan Shawn Feinstein Graduate School at ScholarsArchive@JWU*, 1-12.
- R. J. (2011). The relationship between frequency of Facebook use, participation in Facebook activities, and student engagement. *Computers & Education 58 Elsevier Ltd*, 162-171.
- R. J., E. L., & G. H. (2010). The effect of Twitter on college student engagement and grades. *2010 Blackwell Publishing Ltd Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 1-14.
- W. T., M. M., Khan, M. A., & FaseeUllah. (2012). The Impact of Social Media and Social Networks on Education and Students of Pakistan. *IJCSI International journal of computer science issues*, 9(4), 407-411.